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THE PLACE AND ARTISTIC-AESTHETIC SIGNIFICANCE OF CHIROVS IN KARAKALPAK FOLK FOLKLORE

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Abstract: This article analyzes the role of zhirovs in the oral culture of Karakalpakstan, their creative activity, significance in the epic tradition, and artistic and aesthetic views. The work of zhirovs is considered an important expression of the historical memory, spiritual values, and worldview of the people, and highlights aspects such as their skill in telling epics, poetic language richness, musical and stage style. The study scientifically highlights the artistic skill of zhirovs in creating epic images, the harmony of melody and words, as well as their role in forming the national identity of the Karakalpak people.

Keywords: Karakalpakstan oral culture, zhirov, epic tradition, epic work, artistic and aesthetic views, national culture, folklore, performance skills, epic image, musical heritage.

Introduction.

The issue of “The role and artistic and aesthetic significance of jirovs in the oral culture of Karakalpak people” is one of the topics that requires special attention today not only from the point of view of folklore, but also from the point of view of cultural studies, art history and pedagogy. Because oral culture is a unique expression of the historical memory of the nation, its spiritual world, system of values, ideals and dreams. In the centuries-old creative traditions of the Karakalpak people, jirovs occupy a special position, and they appear as the main creators who shape the voice of the people, the memory of the people and the aesthetic taste of the people.

The jirov person embodies the qualities of not only a poet, but also a musician, singer, lyricist, historian and spiritual educator. In their repertoire, universal themes such as historical events experienced by the people, socio-political changes, the fate of the homeland and the country, the ideas of freedom and justice, love and loyalty, courage and selflessness are artistically expressed. From this perspective, the work of

Karakalpak zhirovs is of incomparable importance in understanding national identity, preserving historical memory, and spiritual and moral education of the younger generation.

Today's globalization, a sharp increase in the flow of information, various manifestations of mass culture have a significant impact on the aesthetic tastes and values of people. In such conditions, the question of the role of ancient oral traditions, in particular, schools of epic poetry and the art of zhirov in the life of society, how to preserve, develop and integrate them into the modern cultural process is becoming relevant. The work of Karakalpak zhirovs is also part of this general process: on the one hand, it is a huge historical and cultural heritage; on the other hand, it is a living art that needs to be brought to today's audience through new interpretations and new media.

Examples of the oral work of the zhirovs should be studied not only as a text, but also as a complex musical-dramatic phenomenon. Because in the process of telling a dostan, words, melody, rhythm, voice timbre, stage movement, communication with the audience - all this forms a holistic aesthetic system. The zhirov deepens the content of the text through the possibilities of his voice, the tone of the musical instrument, pauses and accents, and directly affects the emotions of the listener. For this reason, the traditions of zhirov in the oral work of the Karakalpak people require a separate analysis from an artistic and aesthetic point of view.

The relevance of this article is that, although epics, songs, tales and legends have been studied as a separate direction in the research on Karakalpak oral art, a comprehensive analysis of the artistic and aesthetic views of the zhirovs, their performance style, system of images and musical means of expression based on a single methodological approach has not yet been sufficiently established. In particular, the psychological portrait of the zhirovs as creative individuals, their role in communicating with the people, their individual skills in memorizing, processing and creating new versions of epics require a more in-depth scientific approach.

It is also possible to trace the aesthetic ideal of the people through the work of the Karakalpak zhirovs. The heroes depicted in epics and songs, their moral qualities,

views on beauty, the style of depicting natural landscapes, the variety of images - all this vividly reflects the aesthetic thinking of the Karakalpak people. The zhirov is a mediator who transmits this aesthetic ideal from generation to generation through his voice and his interpretation. Therefore, the role of zhirovs should be assessed not only as performers or storytellers, but also as creators who carry and promote spiritual and aesthetic values.

The article aims to determine the place of zhirovs in the oral culture of Karakalpakstan, analyze their creative activity based on written and oral sources, and highlight the artistic means of telling epics, poetic language, and musical expression. At the same time, the aesthetic views of zhirovs, the moral and ethical ideas reflected in their work, and the artistic interpretation of concepts such as patriotism, humanism, courage, and loyalty will also be in the focus of the research. In this process, modern folklore approaches, comparative analysis, musicology, and cultural studies methods will be used in harmony.

Thus, this article, dedicated to the topic “The role and artistic and aesthetic significance of jirovs in Karakalpak oral folk art”, serves not only to rediscover the work of representatives of the traditional school of epic poetry, but also to reassess their place in our spiritual life today, to show the prospects for using the art of jirovs in the process of forming national identity and aesthetic taste in the minds of the younger generation. In this sense, the results of the research will have scientific and practical significance aimed at a deeper understanding of Karakalpak oral folk art, the preservation of national cultural heritage and its integration into the modern educational process.

Discussion:

In the process of analyzing the role and artistic and aesthetic significance of jirovs in Karakalpak oral folk art, a number of theoretical and practical conclusions can be drawn. First of all, the study shows that the tradition of zhirov is manifested as a complex cultural phenomenon that embodies the epic thinking, historical memory and aesthetic ideal of the Karakalpak people. Since the zhirov combines the qualities of a poet, singer, musician, narrator, historian and spiritual mentor, he appears not only as

an artist, but also as a subject that shapes social consciousness and strengthens the system of values. From this perspective, zhirovs in Karakalpak oral literature are not only performers who tell epics, but also spiritual leaders who artistically express and direct the worldview of the people.

During the research, it was found that although the epic image system, the character of the heroes, and the depiction of their moral and aesthetic qualities in the works of the Karakalpak zhirovs are close to the Turkic epic traditions, local characteristics, that is, the spirit, mentality, customs and values peculiar to the Karakalpak people, are very clearly felt. For example, in the epics, ideas such as protecting the Motherland and the land, sacrificing one's life for the people and the homeland, loyalty to one's word and loyalty, respect for the elderly, and love for the young are manifested as the main content direction. Although these aspects are also found in the epics of other Turkic peoples, in the Karakalpak environment, their interpretation is reflected in the natural landscapes of the Aral Sea, household details specific to the region, local toponyms and historical events. Thus, in the works of the zhirovs, universal ideas are expressed in harmony with the national color.

From an artistic and aesthetic point of view, the art of jirov is of particular importance not only for the content of the text, but also for its performance, musical interpretation, and harmony of voice and instrument. If the text of the epic is somewhat impressive when read in written form, listening to it in jirov performance creates a completely different aesthetic experience. The jirov skillfully uses the timbre, range, rhythm, and intonation changes to emphasize the dramatic points of the events, softens the tone in places where lyrical elements are intensified, and makes the hero's inner experiences more deeply felt through musical means. Thus, the aesthetic value of the oral epic text is revealed mainly in the process of live performance, and this aspect fundamentally distinguishes it from contemporary written literature and screen art. One of the important issues that should be discussed is the continuity and continuity of the jirov tradition in modern conditions. Under the influence of globalization, mass culture, digital platforms, and rapid information flow, the aesthetic tastes, interests, and cultural consumption habits of young people are changing dramatically. In this process,

dangerous trends are observed, such as the narrowing of the audience for ancient doston and jiro traditions, the decline of live performance sessions, and the weakening of the master-student school. However, at the same time, it would be one-sided to think that these traditions are completely disappearing. Because in some regions, the creation of jiros is being revived through doston nights, cultural events, folklore festivals, and expeditions, as well as radio and television broadcasts. Now the Internet, social networks, and video platforms also allow for the promotion of doston in a new way.

At this point, an important question arises: if the art of jirov is popularized through modern means, will its original artistic and aesthetic essence be preserved? The answer to this question is complex and multifaceted. On the one hand, doston can reach a wider audience through audio and video recordings, online broadcasts, shortened or reworked versions. On the other hand, in such conditions, the unique atmosphere of live performance, direct communication with the audience, improvisational elements, and the influence of the atmosphere of the meeting are likely to be significantly weakened. Therefore, without denying modern technologies, but through them, the issue of preserving not the form of life of dostonism, but its inner essence and aesthetic value remains relevant.

Discussing the spiritual and educational role of jirovs, we see that their work still has great potential in forming in the minds of the younger generation values such as awareness of national identity, patriotism, humanity, justice, and hard work. In epics, the victory of evil and oppression, the triumph of justice and truth, the depiction of an ideal personality model through the images of a loyal friend, a selfless young man, a wise woman, and wise parents serve as a direct moral criterion for young people. From this perspective, the work of Karakalpak zhirovs can be used as an effective pedagogical tool in the modern education system, in particular in music, native language and literature, history, spirituality, as well as in classroom and extracurricular educational activities. However, practice shows that the teaching of Karakalpak oral art, in particular the traditions of zhirovs, in secondary schools, colleges, and higher educational institutions is often limited to providing theoretical information. Methods such as listening to live performance samples, organizing meetings with zhirovs,

involving students and pupils in performing certain sections of the epic, staging, and conducting interactive classes are rarely used. This creates the danger of perceiving the oral tradition only as a “heritage of the past”, isolating it from today's life processes. In fact, the art of jirov should be taught and interpreted as a living, creative, active art form based on improvisation. Another aspect that needs to be discussed is the issue of the adaptation of Karakalpak jirovs to the general traditions of epic poetry, while maintaining their creative individuality. Each jirov differs from the other in its voice, style of playing instruments, way of interpreting the epic, and the skill of “putting the characters into the role” through voice. The same epic can evoke different emotional and aesthetic impressions in the performance of different jirovs. However, they operate within certain performance norms, rules, and stylistic traditions. This phenomenon demonstrates the complex harmony of individuality and collectivity in the oral tradition. Although the folklore text belongs to the people, each performance belongs to a specific artist. From this point of view, it is important to study both folk creativity and individual performing art together when assessing the artistic and aesthetic significance of Karakalpak jirovs.

Conclusion.

This study comprehensively analyzed the role of jirovs in Karakalpak oral folk art, their artistic and aesthetic significance, performing skills, and spiritual and educational functions in the life of society. Studies show that the art of jirov is a vivid expression of the centuries-old historical memory, epic thinking, and aesthetic ideals of the Karakalpak people, and is an important cultural phenomenon that transmits the national identity, cultural heritage, and moral values of the people from generation to generation.

The research revealed that in the conditions of globalization and mass culture, preserving the traditions of jirovism and promoting them in a manner appropriate to the modern cultural environment is one of the urgent tasks. Although the fact that the work of the jirovs reaches a wide audience through digital platforms, audio and video recordings, folklore festivals and creative projects is a positive phenomenon, it is important to ensure the continuity of the live performance environment, the tradition

of the master-student and the natural creative environment. Because it is in this tradition and the living performance environment that the inner aesthetic essence of the art of jirovs is fully manifested.

The results of the study also showed that there are opportunities for effective use of the work of the Karakalpak jirovs in the educational process. In particular, studying epics in live performance samples, staging them, organizing creative workshops and meetings through music, literature, history and spirituality can serve as an important pedagogical resource in understanding national identity, forming aesthetic taste and strengthening spiritual and moral values in the younger generation.

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